

Synthesis and Herbicidal Activity of α -Cyanoalkylidene Acetamides

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A number of amides have been prepared by the reaction of α -cyanoalkylidene acetic acids with different amines. α -Cyanoalkylidene acetic acids are synthesised by the condensation of cyanoacetic acid with cycloalkanones. These amides have been characterised by their ir, pmr and mass spectral data.

SOME biologically important amides have been found to be active against weeds of rice, barley and wheat¹. Butachlor, isoproturon, metoxuron herbicides are commercially used for weeds of rice and wheat possessing active moieties like aromatic system, amide linkage and aliphatic chain. Some new α -cyanoalkylidene acetamides have been synthesised incorporating active moieties like aromatic system, amide linkage, cyano group and heterocyclic system to study their effect on herbicidal activity. α -Cyanoalkylidene acetic acids have been synthesised by the Knoevenagel condensation between cyanoacetic acid and cycloalkanones in presence of ammonium acetate. These acids are transformed to different amides by reacting with various amines, viz. morpholine, cyclohexylamine and 4-amino-2,3-dimethyl-1-phenyl-3-pyrazolin-5-one in the presence of phosphorus oxytrichloride and triethylamine. The structures were confirmed by spectral data and elemental analysis.

Treatment of cyanoacetic acid with cyclopentanone and cycloheptanone in ammonium acetate gave the acids 1 and 5 respectively. The acid (1) was reacted with 4-amino-2,3-dimethyl-1-phenyl-3-pyrazolin-5-one, cyclohexylamine and morpholine

to obtain compounds 2, 3 and 4 respectively. Similarly, the acid (5) was treated with 4-amino-2,3-dimethyl-1-phenyl-3-pyrazolin-5-one to get 6. Structures of the compounds were established by ir, nmr and mass spectral data².

Biological activity³: By considering the relative activity of the compounds 1-4, the herbicidal activity decreased in the order 2 > 3 > 4 > 1. Compound 6 was active at high concentration and inhibited the per cent germination at lower concentration especially in piazis but the root length decreased as the concentration increased.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 337 spectrophotometer, pmr spectra on a EM 390 (90 MHz) spectrophotometer using TMS as internal standard and mass spectra on a Lcol-JMS-D-300 instrument. Silica gel G (B.D.H.) was used for tlc and column chromatography.

Cycloalkylidene cyanoacetic acid. General procedure: A mixture of cyanoacetic acid, ammonium acetate and cycloalkanone in dry benzene was refluxed in a round-bottomed flask equipped with the Dean and Stark apparatus for 10-12 h in an oil-bath. The lower layer was run off to remove all the water formed. After cooling, the reaction mixture was washed with water twice and the organic portion dried over anhydrous calcium chloride. The solvent was then distilled off and the crude product was recrystallised from ethanol-petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) to obtain the pure acid.

Cyclopentylidene cyanoacetic acid (1): The acid (1) was obtained from cyanoacetic acid (0.1 mol), cyclopentanone (0.11 mol) and ammonium acetate (0.0004 mol), (84%), m.p. 137° (Found: C, 63.57; H, 5.95; N, 9.27. $\text{C}_8\text{H}_9\text{NO}_3$ calcd. for: C, 63.54; H, 5.94; N, 9.23%); ν_{max} 3 220, 2 210 and 1 630 cm^{-1} .

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Cycloheptylidene cyanoacetic acid (5): The acid was obtained by treating cyanoacetic acid (0.11 mol), ammonium acetate (0.0004 mol) and cycloheptanone (0.10 mol) in dry benzene (200 ml), (18%), m.p. 85–70° (Found: C, 67.03; H, 7.26; N, 7.82. $C_{10}H_{13}NO_2$ calcd. for: C, 67.02; H, 7.23; N, 7.80%); ν_{max} 3 300, 2 220 and 1 630 cm^{-1} .

N-Amino-2-cyano-2-cycloalkylidene acetamide. General procedure: To a well-stirred solution of cycloalkylidene cyanoacetic acid, triethylamine and amine at 0° in dry dichloromethane, was added a solution of phosphorus oxychloride in dichloromethane, and the triethylamine was added in one instalment. The contents were stirred for 0.5 h at 0° for further 6 h at room temperature. The progress of reaction was checked on tlc plates at regular intervals. The reaction mixture was then decomposed with crushed-ice and extracted with dichloromethane (3 × 20 ml), washed with aqueous sodium carbonate (10%; 3 × 20 ml), water, hydrochloric acid (10%; 3 × 20 ml) and again with water. After drying over anhydrous calcium chloride, solvent was evaporated and the crude product was purified by column chromatography over neutral alumina using petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) and chloroform mixture (1 : 3) as eluent to get the amide.

N-[4(2,3-Dimethyl-1-phenyl-3-pyrazolin-5-one)]yl-2-cyano-2-cyclopentylidene acetamide (2): The acid (1; 0.02 mol) was reacted with triethylamine (0.007 mol), 4-amino-2,3-dimethyl-1-phenyl-3-pyrazolin-5-one (0.02 mol), phosphorus oxychloride (0.018 mol) and triethylamine (0.013 mol) to obtain the amide (2; 41%), m.p. 120° (Found: C, 74.02; H, 6.49; N, 18.18. $C_{19}H_{20}N_4O_2$ calcd. for: C, 74.00; H, 6.44; N, 18.16%); ν_{max} 3 140 (NH), 2 220 (C≡N), 1 630 (C=O) and 840 cm^{-1} (Ar); δ 3.2 (3H, s, NCH₃), 2.2 (3H, s, O=C–C=C–CH₃), 7.3 (1H, s, NHCO exchanged with D₂O), 7.4–7.6 (5H, m, ArH), 2.8–2.9 (4H, m, $\left[\begin{array}{c} -CH_2 \\ | \\ -CH_2 \end{array} \right] =$) and 1.7–1.9 (4H,

m, $\left[\begin{array}{c} H_2C \\ | \\ H_2C \end{array} \right] =$); m/z 336 (M^+ , 100).

N-Cyclohexyl-2-cyano-2-cyclopentylidene acetamide (3): The acid (1) (0.01 mol) was treated with triethylamine (0.0035 mol), cyclohexylamine (0.01 mol), phosphorus oxychloride (0.001 mol) and triethylamine (0.0075 mol) to get the amide (3; 52%), m.p. 110° (Found: C, 72.41; H, 8.62; N, 12.06. $C_{14}H_{20}N_2O$ calcd. for: C, 72.38; H, 8.58; N, 12.03%); ν_{max} 3 300, 2 220 and 1 640 cm^{-1} ; δ 6.0 (1H, s, NHCO exchanged with D₂O), 3.85 (1H, m, HC(CH₂)₂), 1.6–2.1 (10H, m, methylenic protons of

cyclohexyl), 1.1–1.3 (4H, m, $\left[\begin{array}{c} CH_2 \\ | \\ CH_2 \end{array} \right] =$) and 2.7–3.2 (4H, m, $\left[\begin{array}{c} CH_2-CH_2 \\ | \\ CH_2-CH_2 \end{array} \right] =$); m/z 232 (M^+ , 100).

N-(Tetrahydro-1,4-oxazin)yl-2-cyano-2-cyclopentylidene acetamide (4): The acid (1; 0.01 mol) was reacted with triethylamine (0.035 mol), morpholine (0.01 mol), phosphorus oxychloride (0.01 mol) and triethylamine (0.075 mol) to obtain 4 (22%) (Found: C, 65.45; H, 7.27; N, 12.72. $C_{12}H_{16}N_2O_2$ calcd. for: C, 65.40; H, 7.23; N, 12.70%); ν_{max} 2 200, 1 615 and 830 cm^{-1} ; δ 1.8–1.9 (4H, m, $\left[\begin{array}{c} H_2C \\ | \\ H_2C \end{array} \right] =$); 2.6–2.8 (4H, m, $\left[\begin{array}{c} CH_2 \\ | \\ CH_2 \end{array} \right] =$) and 3.7–3.8 (8H, m, –N<math>\left[\begin{array}{c} \diagup \\ \diagdown \end{array} \right]>O).

N-[4(2,3-Dimethyl-1-phenyl-3-pyrazolin-5-one)]yl-2-cyano-2-cycloheptylidene acetamide (6): The acid (5; 0.005 mol) was treated with 4-amino-2,3-dimethyl-1-phenyl-3-pyrazolin-5-one (0.005 mol), triethylamine (0.0018 mol) and phosphorus oxychloride (0.005 mol) to get 6 (39%) (Found: C, 69.23; H, 6.59; N, 15.38. $C_{21}H_{24}N_4O_2$ calcd. for: C, 69.20; H, 6.54; N, 15.36%); ν_{max} 3 300, 2 200 and 1 630 cm^{-1} ; δ 3.1 (3H, s, NCH₃), 2.2 (3H, s, O=C–C=C–CH₃), 7.9 (1H, NHCO exchanged with D₂O), 7.5 (5H, m, ArH) and 1.4–1.9 (12H, methylenic protons).

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